

NUTRIENT DEFICIENCY IN SILPHIUM INTEGRIFOLIUM

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Methods

This project aimed to characterize the symptoms of various nutrient deficiencies in *Silphium integrifolium* (silphium, silflower, rosinweed) in order to help growers and researchers identify nutrient deficiencies in their plantings.

To do this, 5-week-old silphium plants were grown hydroponically in a greenhouse setting in net pots. Plants were fed a fertilizer solution containing either all the necessary nutrients or all the necessary nutrients minus one; these plants missing a specific nutrient (nitrogen, for example) are called deficient in this guide, assuming they need some amount of the nutrient higher than none. After 5.5 weeks in these treatment nutrient solutions, we took pictures of leaves and roots, described visible symptoms of nutrient stress, measured heights of plants from the base of the leaves to the tips, and weighed dried biomass. Leaf biomass is the dried weight of all aboveground plant matter. Root biomass is the dried weight of all roots. All images shown here were taken after 5.5 weeks of treatment unless otherwise noted. The black dots in the photographs are used for scale: the length of a row of dots is about 4 inches.

All plants in this study shared a single mother and had various fathers. This genetic similarity made finding common symptoms easier but might have caused us to miss symptoms that may appear differently based on genetics. This study is also limited by not following the plants through a "winter-time" nor through flowering and grain production. The pictures and descriptions here are a starting point and we welcome and encourage feedback about what you're seeing in your plantings!

Nitrogen (N)

A

B

C

D

A. Nitrogen-deficient plant. Leaves appear smaller and yellow-green compared to control leaves. **B. Healthy control plant** with dark green leaves. **C. Nitrogen-deficient roots.** N-deficient plants have reduced root biomass compared to **D. Healthy control roots.**

Nitrogen (N)

A

B

C

A. Healthy control leaf B.-C. Nitrogen-deficient leaves

Leaves appear smaller than those of healthy plants. Leaves are a lighter green or yellowed compared to control plants. Yellowing is relatively even across the leaves (not constricted to between veins or the tip or base of the leaf). New leaves emerge already lighter green. Some older leaves turn brown and die off. New growth is slow and plants have reduced height and leaf biomass compared to control plants.

Potassium (K)

A

B

C

D

A. Potassium-deficient plant. K-deficient plants have ruffled leaves and brown dead spots creeping in from the leaf tips and edges. Leaves die back in multiple shades of brown. **B. Healthy control plant.** **C. Potassium-deficient roots.** Some roots are brown and slightly mushy. Root biomass is reduced compared to **D. Healthy control roots.**

Potassium (K)

A

B

A. Healthy control leaf B. Potassium-deficient leaves

Leaves appear smaller than those of healthy plants and are ruffled (do not lie flat). Brown dead patches creep in from the leaf tips and edges and appear as different shades of brown in one spot (like a coffee stain). Some leaves have yellowing in large patches between veins. When yellowing occurs, it is most severe near the leaf tip or edges.

New leaves emerge smaller but otherwise appear healthy at the start. Older leaves are often symptomatic.

Potassium-deficient silphium plants have reduced height and leaf biomass compared to control plants.

Phosphorous (P)

A. Phosphorous-deficient plant. P-deficient leaves are smaller than controls, but emerge a similar shade of dark green to controls. Primarily older leaves die back from the edges or in brown patches. **B. Healthy control plant.** **C. Phosphorous-deficient roots.** Roots appear to branch less than controls. Root biomass is reduced compared to **D. Healthy control roots.**

Phosphorous (P)

A

B

A. Healthy control leaf B. Phosphorous-deficient leaves

P-deficient leaves are overall smaller (narrower and shorter) and feel thicker and courser to the touch compared to controls.

Leaves emerge dark green but die off as they get older. Leaves die back starting with brown patches at the leaf edges or in grey-brown patches in the middle of the leaves.

Plant height and leaf biomass is reduced with phosphorous-deficiency.

Sulfur (S)

A

B

C

D

A. Sulfur-deficient plant. S-deficient leaves seem smaller and narrower than controls and are slightly and evenly yellowed. **B. Healthy control plant.** **C. Sulfur-deficient roots.** Root biomass is reduced compared to **D. Healthy control roots.**

Sulfur (S)

A. Healthy control leaf. B. Sulfur-deficient leaf. S-deficient plants had visibly smaller leaves than control plants as well as reduced height and leaf biomass.

S-deficient plants can be differentiated from N-deficient plants by the fact that their older leaves don't seem to die off, and leaf color is uniform across each leaf and across the plant.

Calcium (Ca)

Calcium-deficient plants were not able to grow any new leaves or roots and thus had reduced height, leaf and root biomass compared to healthy control plants. These photos were taken after 2 weeks of being on treatment solution. All the Ca-deficient plants died within 1.5-2.5 weeks of transplanting. Less severe calcium-deficiency may produce different or more distinctive symptoms.

Calcium (Ca)

A

A. Calcium-deficient plant.

Leaves are small, dried out, and yellowed. Plants put on no new leaf or root growth. Existing roots are brown and mushy.

B

C

B-C. Control plants. Silphium leaves and roots at the same timepoint post-transplanting.

Magnesium (Mg)

A

B

A. Healthy control leaf B. Magnesium-deficient leaves

Mg-deficient leaves appear ruffled at the edges and slightly smaller than control leaves. Areas around the central vein and immediate offshoot veins are dark green. On many leaves, in-between these veins the leaves are lighter green, yellow, or even a burnt ochre.

Visibly symptomatic leaves tend to be neither the oldest nor the newest leaves.

Height and leaf biomass of magnesium-deficient leaves are reduced compared to controls.

Magnesium (Mg)

A. Magnesium-deficient plant. The undersides of Mg-deficient leaf veins sometimes have brown patches but appear normal from the top. Brown patches are present on some leaves, usually at the leaf edge. **B. Healthy control plant.** **C. Magnesium-deficient roots.** Roots appear to branch less than controls. Root biomass is reduced compared to **D. Healthy control roots.**

Iron (Fe)

A. Healthy control leaf B. Iron-deficient leaves

Iron-deficient leaves pictured here from left to right are arranged oldest to youngest. Iron deficiency is characterized by yellowing between the leaf veins and is most severe in younger leaves. As the deficiency becomes more severe, the younger leaves can emerge yellow or even white.

Yellowing tends to happen evenly from the tip to the base of the leaf, though occasionally there can be a subtle color gradient within a leaf.

Iron-deficient silphium plants have reduced height and leaf biomass.

Iron (Fe)

A. Iron-deficient plant. Iron deficiency produces yellowing between the veins in moderate cases but can turn entire young leaves white when severe, **B. Healthy control plant.** **C. Iron-deficient roots.** Root biomass is reduced compared to **D. Healthy control roots.**

Boron (B)

A

B

A. Healthy control leaf **B. Boron-deficient leaves**

Boron-deficient plants have a variety of symptoms, not all of which are always present on the same plant. Yellowing occurs mostly between the main leaf veins and is most severe near the leaf tip. Leaves will occasionally form dead patches ranging in color from brown to white. These dead patches most often form at the leaf tips or edges.

New leaves emerge with restricted width, and the edges can look constricted.

Boron-deficient silphium plants have reduced height and leaf biomass.

Boron (B)

A. Boron-deficient plant. The most distinctive symptom of boron-deficiency in silphium is narrowing of new leaves and the pinched leaf edges, like a rubber band was stretched across the width of a leaf. **B. Healthy control plant.** **C. Boron-deficient roots.** Boron-deficient roots have small brown bumps along them. Root biomass is reduced compared to **D. Healthy control roots.**

Zinc (Zn)

A. Zinc-deficient plant. Zinc deficient plants may appear to have light green marbling, especially between the veins. **B. Healthy control plant.** **C. Zinc-deficient roots.** Root biomass is reduced compared to **D. Healthy control roots.**

Zinc (Zn)

A. Healthy control leaf **B. Zinc-deficient leaves**

Zinc-deficient plants are characterized by slight light green marbled leaves and/or leaves with a dark green mid-vein and immediate branching veins surrounded by slightly lighter green leaf tissue.

Symptoms appeared on leaves of almost any age, but new leaves emerged looking healthy.

Zinc-deficient silphium plants have reduced height and leaf biomass.